

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX
METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART I. COMPOSITION
OF COPPER FERROCYANIDE BY THERMOMETRIC METHOD

BY ABANI K. BHATTACHARYA AND HARISH C. GAUR

Composition of copper ferrocyanide has been investigated by thermometric method. From the breaks in the direct titration curves, the compound $K_2CuFeCy_6$, first formed with excess of $CuSO_4$, changes to $K_2Cu_2(FeCy_6)_2$.

The composition of copper ferrocyanide has been investigated by several workers both by purely analytical methods and by physico-chemical methods. But there is hardly any co-ordination of the views expressed by them. Wyrubow (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1905, viii, 5,444) prepared three compounds corresponding to Cu_2FeCy_6 ; $K_2CuFeCy_6$, K_4FeCy_6 and $KCuFeCy_6$, under varying conditions. Müller, Wegelin and Kellerhoff (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1912, ii, 86, 82) investigated the composition of the precipitates formed by the interaction of copper sulphate with potassium ferrocyanide, and with hydroferrocyanic acid, in various proportions in 0.1M. aqueous solutions, and they were of the opinion that a precipitate of a constant composition could be obtained only when one of the two components was in large excess. For the intermediate values of the ratio $CuSO_4/K_4FeCy_6$, several compounds of variable compositions were obtained. Williams ("The Chemistry of Cyanogen Compounds", pp. 103-104) found that the compounds $K_4Cu_2(FeCy_6)_2$ was formed when potassium ferrocyanide was precipitated exactly by a cupric salt. In the presence of a large excess of potassium ferrocyanide the precipitate corresponded to $K_{12}Cu_2(FeCy_6)_2$, while in the presence of a large excess of copper salt, the composition of the precipitate was found to be $K_2Cu_2(FeCy_6)_2$. Rauter (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1895, 8, 315) was of the opinion that copper ferrocyanide adsorbed some potassium ferrocyanide, and due to the colloidal nature of the precipitate it peptised before it could be washed entirely free of it. This suggested that purely analytical methods could not be of much use in determining the composition of copper ferrocyanide.

Kolthoff (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1923, 62, 209) employing the method of conductometric titrations observed that at first the normal salt, Cu_2FeCy_6 , was precipitated, which with further quantity of the reagent formed the double salt $K_2Cu_2(FeCy_6)_2$, followed by a third inflection point corresponding to the formation of $K_4Cu_2(FeCy_6)_2$. But Britton and Dodd (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1543) following the same method did not confirm these results; they obtained two inflections corresponding to the formations of Cu_2FeCy_6 , xK_4FeCy_6 , where $x=0.16$ and 0.40 .

In view of the conflicting opinions it was considered worthwhile to study the composition of this compound by thermometric, conductometric and potentiometric methods to arrive at a more definite conclusion. In this paper only the results of thermometric titrations have been included and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric titration arrangement was similar to that adopted by Halder (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 147). The reagents used were of 'Analar' (B. D. H.) quality.

Standard solution of copper sulphate was prepared by direct weighing. Potassium ferrocyanide solution was estimated by titrating against standardised potassium permanganate solution (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Part II, p. 536).

Using the different concentrations of the two salts in solutions the titrations were followed by the direct and the reverse methods, *i. e.* when copper sulphate solution from burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide taken in the Dewar flask and *vice versa*. Titrations were also carried in the presence of alcohol, up to the total concentration of 20% by volume.

A/1-Copper sulphate solution (containing 31.344 g. CuSO_4 per litre) corresponds to $M/5.09$ solution. A/1-Potassium ferrocyanide solution (containing 84.494 g. of K_4FeCy_6 , $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ per litre) corresponds to $M/5.0$ solution.

Direct Thermometric Titrations

Copper sulphate solution from a burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide taken in the flask, and mixed with varying amounts of alcohol.

TABLE I

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 soln. = 20 c. c. Alcohol = nil (Fig. 1, curve 1).

A/2- CuSO_4 added	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c. c.	0.000	3.0 c.c.	0.180	6.0 c.c.	0.330
0.5	0.030	3.5	0.210	6.5	0.345
1.0	0.060	4.0	0.230	7.0	0.355
1.5	0.090	4.5	0.255	7.5	0.365
2.0	0.120	5.0	0.280	8.0	0.370
2.5	0.150	5.5	0.305	8.5	0.385

TABLE II

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 soln. = 18 c. c. Alcohol = 2 c. c. (Fig. 2, curve 2).

A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c. c.	0.000	2.5 c. c.	0.110	4.5 c. c.	0.200	6.5 c. c.	0.260
1.0	0.030	3.0	0.130	5.0	0.225	7.0	0.265
1.5	0.050	3.5	0.155	5.5	0.240	7.5	0.270
2.0	0.075	4.0	0.180	6.0	0.255	8.0	0.275

TABLE III

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 soln. = 16 c. c. Alcohol = 4 c. c. (Fig. 2, curve 3).

A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.	A/2- CuSO_4 added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c. c.	0.000	3.0 c.c.	0.190	6.0 c.c.	0.295
0.5	0.030	3.5	0.210	6.5	0.300
1.0	0.060	4.0	0.235	7.0	0.305
1.5	0.095	4.5	0.260	7.5	0.310
2.0	0.130	5.5	0.290	8.0	0.315

TABLE IV

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 20 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 3, curve 4).

A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c. c.	0.000	8.0 c. c.	0.190	14.0 c. c.	0.340
1.0	0.020	9.0	0.230	15.0	0.355
2.0	0.045	10.0	0.250	16.0	0.370
4.0	0.100	11.0	0.275	17.0	0.380
6.0	0.155	12.0	0.300	18.0	0.395
7.0	0.180	13.0	0.325		

TABLE V

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 18 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 3, curve 5).

A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	5.5 c.c.	0.240	9.5 c.c.	0.390
0.5	0.025	6.5	0.280	10.5	0.410
1.5	0.065	7.0	0.305	11.0	0.425
2.5	0.110	8.0	0.335	12.0	0.445
3.5	0.160	8.5	0.350	13.0	0.465
4.5	0.200	9.0	0.365	13.5	0.475

TABLE VI

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 16 c.c. Alcohol = 4 c.c. (Fig. 3, curve 6).

A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-CuSO ₄ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	5.0 c.c.	0.435	9.0 c.c.	0.665
1.0	0.165	6.0	0.500	10.0	0.695
2.0	0.205	7.0	0.560	11.0	0.730
3.0	0.280	8.0	0.615	12.0	0.755
4.0	0.370			12.5	0.765

Reverse Thermometric Titrations

Potassium ferrocyanide from a burette was added to copper sulphate solution in the Dewar flask, and mixed with varying amounts of alcohol.

TABLE VII

A/10-CuSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 4, curve 7).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	2.5 c.c.	0.100	6.0 c.c.	0.200
0.5	0.020	3.0	0.120	7.0	0.210
1.0	0.040	3.5	0.140	8.0	0.220
1.5	0.060	4.0	0.160	9.0	0.230
2.0	0.080	5.0	0.190	9.5	0.235

TABLE VIII

A/10-CuSO₄ soln. = 18 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 4, curve 8).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	2.5 c.c.	0.115	5.5 c.c.	0.215	7.5 c.c.	0.255
1.0	0.045	3.0	0.140	6.0	0.225	8.0	0.265
1.5	0.070	4.0	0.185	6.5	0.235	8.5	0.275
2.0	0.090	5.0	0.210	7.0	0.245	9.0	0.285

TABLE IX

A/10-CuSO₄ soln. = 16 c.c. Alcohol = 4 c.c. (Fig. 4, curve 9).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	3.0 c.c.	0.250	6.0 c.c.	0.370
1.0	0.090	3.5	0.285	7.0	0.385
1.5	0.135	4.5	0.335	7.5	0.395
2.0	0.180	5.0	0.345	8.0	0.405
2.5	0.220	5.5	0.355	8.5	0.415

TABLE X

A/10-CuSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 5, curve 10).

A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	5.5	0.220	10.5 c.c.	0.415
0.5	0.012	6.5	0.260	11.5	0.450
1.5	0.055	7.5	0.305	12.5	0.475
2.5	0.095	8.5	0.350	13.5	0.500
3.5	0.135	9.5	0.390	14.5	0.525
4.5	0.175			15.0	0.535

TABLE XI

A/10-CuSO₄ soln. = 18 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 5, curve 11).

A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	3.0 c.c.	0.105	7.0 c.c.	0.240	14.0 c.c.	0.330
0.5	0.010	4.0	0.140	8.0	0.260	12.0	0.350
1.0	0.030	5.0	0.170	9.0	0.290	13.0	0.370
2.0	0.075	6.0	0.205	10.0	0.310	14.0	0.390

TABLE XII

A/10-CuSO₄ = 16 c.c. Alcohol = 4 c.c. (Fig. 5, curve 12).

A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	0.000	5.0 c.c.	0.410	9.0	0.590
2.0	0.200	6.0	0.460	10.0	0.610
2.5	0.240	7.0	0.515	11.0	0.630
3.0	0.280	8.0	0.560	12.0	0.650
4.5	0.380			13.0	0.670

Direct Thermometric Titrations (curves 1-6)

TABLE XIII

(i) A/2-CuSO₄ and A/10-K₄FeCy₆

Conc. ratio (n)=5:1.

Vol of A/10-K ₄ FeCy ₆ in the thermos-flask (v)	Alcohol added	A/2-CuSO ₄ reqd for K ₄ FeCy ₆ in the thermos (v ₁)		A/2-CuSO ₄ calc for 20 c.c. of A/10 K ₄ FeCy ₆ (v ₁ /v) 20		Equiv. vol of A/10-CuSO ₄ n (20v ₁ /v).		Curve No
		I Break.	II Break.	I Break.	II Break.	I Break.	II Break.	
		20.0 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	4.16 c.c.	6.32 c.c.	4.16 c.c.	6.32 c.c.	
18.0	2.0	3.70	5.65	4.11	6.28	20.55	31.4	2
16.0	4.0	3.20	5.00	4.00	6.25	20.00	31.25	3

(ii) A/4-CuSO₄ and A/10-K₄FeCy₆

Conc. ratio (n)=2.5:1.

20.0 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	8.35 c.c.	12.6 c.c.	8.35 c.c.	12.6 c.c.	20.87 c.c.	31.5 c.c.	4
16.0	4.0	6.45	10.0	8.00	12.50	20.15	31.2	6

The tables show that the amount of copper sulphate required for 20 c.c. of potassium ferrocyanide decreases as the amount of alcohol is increased.

Reverse Thermometric Titrations (curves 7-12)

TABLE XIV

(i) A/4-K₄FeCy₆ and A/10-CuSO₄. Conc. ratio (n)=2.5:1.

Vol. of A/10-CuSO ₄ in the thermos flask (v)	Alcohol added.	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ reqd for CuSO ₄ in the thermos flask (v ₁)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ calc. for 20 c.c. of A/10 CuSO ₄ (20 v ₁ /v)	Equiv. vol of A/10-K ₄ FeCy ₆ n(20 v ₁ /v)	Curve No.
20.0 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	4.8 c.c.	4.8 c.c.	12.0 c.c.	7
18.0	2.0	4.40	4.89	12.2	8
16.0	4.0	4.0	5.00	12.5	9

(ii) A/8-K₄FeCy₆ and A/10-CuSO₄. Conc. ratio (n)=4:5.

20.0 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	10
18.0	2.0	9.05	10.06	12.6	11
16.0	4.0	8.20	10.25	12.81	12

The tables show that the amount of K₄FeCy₆ required for 20 c.c. of CuSO₄ increases as the amount of alcohol is increased.

DISCUSSION

Considering the strength of the solutions of copper sulphate (*M*/5.09) and potassium ferrocyanide (*M*/5), theoretical titre values required for the 20 c.c. of K₄FeCy₆ for the formation of the compounds K₂CuFeCy₆, Cu₂FeCy₆, and K₂Cu₂(FeCy₆)₂ in direct titrations would be 20.38, 40.76, and 30.56 c.c. respectively of copper sulphate solution. For the reverse titrations, the theoretical titre values for 20 c.c. of copper sulphate

solution for the formation of the above compounds would be 19.64, 9.82, and 13.08 c.c. respectively of potassium ferrocyanide solution.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

In the curves for direct titrations (Fig. 1, 2, and 3) there are two breaks and the observed titre values correspond approximately to the formation of the compounds

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

$K_2CuFeCy_6$ and $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$. In the reverse case (Fig. 4 and 5), there is only one break which corresponds approximately to the formation of $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$. The pure compound Cu_2FeCy_6 is not formed in either of the cases.

The discrepancy between the observed titre values (Tables XIII, XIV) and the theoretical ones given above, is explained on the tendency of the compound formed to hydrolyse. Then potassium ferrocyanide thus released would react with more of copper sulphate with the result that the titre values in aqueous solution would be greater in direct titrations and less in the reverse titrations than the theoretical values. The effect of addition of alcohol in increasing amounts in direct titrations is the gradual decrease in the observed titre values; in the reverse titrations, an increase is observed under the same conditions. This can be explained as due to the check of the hydrolysis of the compound. Then the observed titre values in presence of increasing amounts of alcohol should correspond more closely to the theoretical values in the direct and the reverse titrations. This has been actually observed.

The adsorption of Cu^+ and $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ ions by copper ferrocyanide should not, however, be altogether ignored. The effect of adsorption of these ions from the surrounding solution, by the precipitate, would be to decrease the titre values in aqueous medium in both the cases, which should then increase in the presence of alcohol. This is observed only in the reverse titrations, whereas there is a decrease in the titre value in the direct titration in presence of alcohol. This suggests that the role of hydrolysis is more predominant in the precipitation of copper ferrocyanide. This fact was ignored by previous authors and hence conflicting views on the composition of copper ferrocyanide were given.

From the breaks in the direct titration curves (Fig. 1 to 3) it appears that the compound $K_2CuFeCy_6$ is first formed which with excess of copper sulphate changes to $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$, the latter corresponding to the second break in the curves. In the reverse cases, the titration is carried in presence of excess of copper sulphate and hence the break corresponding to $K_2CuFeCy_6$ is not observed.

Thermometric titration results support the conclusions of Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) so far as the formation of the compounds $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$ is concerned. The inflection in the conductivity curves obtained by him corresponding to the formation of $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$ is not supported.

FIG. 5.

The work has been extended by the study of conductometric and potentiometric titrations along with hydrolysis and adsorption which will be communicated through separate papers.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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